

Report of Study on the Effect of a Nutrition Food on Nutritional Supplement for Persons in Menstrual Period

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1. Abstract

Dysmenorrhea is one of the most common gynecological symptoms. Once it occurs, dysmenorrhea will cause discomforts such as lower abdominal pain in women. At the same time, it has a high incidence in population, which greatly affects the normal quality of life of female patients. At present, there is no particularly effective drugs for dysmenorrhea. Traditional drugs for dysmenorrhea are mainly non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). However, the efficacy of the drugs is not enough. Moreover, they are accompanied by serious side effects. Therefore, it is urgent to provide effective strategies for prevention and control. Our study found a reasonable nutritional diet that can effectively improve the symptoms of dysmenorrhea. We recruited multinational sufferers of dysmenorrhea and menoxenia and conducted an international population nutrition intervention trial to explore the effect of composite fruit and vegetable nutrition supplements on dysmenorrhea sufferers. Our findings showed that nutrition foods containing composite components of fruits, vegetables and plants can greatly improve the symptoms of dysmenorrhea.

2. Introduction

Dysmenorrhea is one of the most common gynecological symptoms.

Premenstrual/post-menstrual or menstrual simultaneous phenomena include lower abdomen pain, heaviness or other troubles. Dysmenorrhea includes primary dysmenorrhea and secondary dysmenorrhea. Primary dysmenorrhea is that without physical lesions in reproductive organs, and secondary dysmenorrhea is that caused by physical lesions in pelvic cavity[1]. However, women themselves have insufficient diagnosis and treatment of dysmenorrhea, and even underestimate the significance of treatment. As a result, quality of life of women is seriously impaired, e.g., limitation on daily activities and mental pressure[2]. It is reported that incidence of primary dysmenorrhea in women of different ages and nationalities can be up to 45%-97%, accounting for 1%-3% of causes of absence from school and work [3]. Therefore, it is urgent to provide effective strategies for prevention and control.

At present, there is no particularly effective medicine for dysmenorrhea. The traditional drugs for dysmenorrhea are mainly non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). However, whether NSAIDs are the best clinic choice is uncertain, and NSAIDs have serious side effects such as headache, dizziness, serious gastroenteric reaction and acne. As a result, the application of NSAIDs is limited[4].

Results of previous randomized controlled trial showed that reasonable nutritional diets could effectively relieve symptoms of dysmenorrhea[5]. However, many women have difficulties in getting rich and reasonable nutritional diets. Preliminary study of our team found a nutrition food, containing composite components of fruits, vegetables and plants, that has potential effect for relieving symptom of dysmenorrhea. In the present study, we recruited multinational sufferers of dysmenorrhea and menoxenia and conducted an international population nutrition intervention trial to explore the effect of composite fruit and vegetable nutrition supplements on dysmenorrhea sufferers.

3. Methods and materials

3.1 Test on nutritional supplement for primary dysmenorrhea sufferers

3.1.1 Object of study

100 persons conforming to the following inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected:

Inclusion criteria: those diagnosed as primary dysmenorrhea sufferers.

Exclusion criteria: objects that are identified by researchers as unsuitable for the experiment.

3.1.2 Testing program

The study was a randomized double-blind controlled test, in which, the objects were randomly divided into two groups, with 50 persons for experimental group and 50 persons for control group. The experimental group took a piece of nutritious food orally every day (0.6g composite components of vegetables, fruits and plants; trade name: (Bengongbupa); manufacturer: Guangzhou Hutongyouwu Biotechnology Co., Ltd.); and the control group took a tablet of placebo every day. The experiment lasted for 3 months, during which, contraception measures by other means than drugs were taken, and the objects periodically attended E-questionnaire survey.

3.1.3 Observation indicators

Objects of the study were trained on periodic self-assessment and report of dysmenorrhea through standard electronic questionnaire.

3.2 Test on nutritional supplement for secondary dysmenorrhea sufferers

3.2.1 Object of study

100 persons conforming to the following inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected:

Inclusion criteria: those diagnosed as secondary dysmenorrhea sufferers.

Exclusion criteria: objects that are identified by researchers as unsuitable for the experiment.

3.2.2 Testing program

The study was a randomized double-blind controlled test, in which, the objects of study were randomly divided into two groups, with 50 persons for experimental group and 50 persons for control group. The experimental group took a piece of nutritious food orally every day (0.6g composite components of vegetables, fruits and plants; trade name: (Bengongbupa); manufacturer: Guangzhou Hutongyouwu Biotechnology Co., Ltd.); and the control group took a tablet of placebo every day. The experiment lasted for 3 months, during which, contraception measures by other means than drugs were taken, and the objects were periodically visited.

3.2.3 Observation indicators

Ask and record menstrual pain (visual analog scale (VAS)).

3.3 Test on nutritional supplement for menoxenia sufferers

3.3.1 Object of study

100 persons conforming to the following inclusion and exclusion criteria were selected:

Inclusion criterion: those who had been diagnosed as menoxenia sufferer (menoxenia include unusual increase of menstrual bleeding and unusual prolonged duration of menstrual bleeding).

Exclusion criteria: objects that are identified by researchers as unsuitable for the test.

3.3.2 Testing program

The study was a randomized double-blind controlled test, in which, the objects of study were randomly divided into two groups, with 50 persons for experimental group and 50 persons for control group. The test group took a piece of nutritious food orally every day (0.6g composite components of vegetables, fruits and plants; trade name: (Bengongbupa); manufacturer: Guangzhou Hutongyouwu Biotechnology Co., Ltd.); and the control group took a tablet of placebo every day. The test lasted for 3 months, during which, contraception measures by other means than drugs were taken, and the objects were periodically visited.

3.3.3 Observation indicators

Situations in menstrual period were measured and recorded, including duration of menses, number of pieces of sanitary towels used and sanitary towel weight.

3.4 Statistical analysis

SPSS 22.0 software was used for statistical analysis. All hypothesis tests were two-tailed tests, with the level of statistical significance set to $P < 0.05$. Inter-group difference of normally distributed continuous variables underwent test or variance analysis; variables that are not normally distributed were log transformed and then subject to t test or variance analysis; inter-group difference of classified variables was subject to χ^2 test.

4. Result

4.1 Nutritional supplements relieved primary dysmenorrhea

Experimental group: 98% of the sufferers had alleviated dysmenorrhea compared with the situation before the test.

Control group: less than 20% of the sufferers had alleviated dysmenorrhea compared with the situation before the test.

As compared with the control group, the experimental group taking dietary supplement had alleviated primary dysmenorrhea (as shown in Table 1).

Table 1. Nutritional supplements relieved primary dysmenorrhea.

Proportion of persons having alleviated primary dysmenorrhea (self-assessment)		
Time of assessment	The group taking nutrition foods (50 persons)	Control group (50 persons)
1 month	86%	18%
3 months	98%	12%

4.2 Nutritional supplements relieved secondary dysmenorrhea

As compared with the control group, the experimental group taking dietary supplements had alleviated primary dysmenorrhea (as shown in on Fig.1 and Fig.2) and is of statistical significance ($p < 0.01$).

Fig.1 Nutrition food significantly reduced dysmenorrhea index of secondary dysmenorrhea.

Fig.2 Nutrition food relieved secondary dysmenorrhea.

4.3 Nutritional supplements relieved menoxenia

Experimental group: as compared with the situation before the test, duration of menstrual bleeding was reduced from 2 weeks to about 1 week ($p < 0.01$) (as shown on Fig.3); volume of menstrual bleeding was significantly reduced ($p < 0.01$) (as shown on Fig.4 and Fig.5).

Control group: as compared with the situation before the test, there was no significantly improvement in duration of menses and volume of menstrual bleeding

As compared with the control group, the experimental group taking dietary supplements had significantly alleviated menoxenia ($p < 0.01$).

Fig.3 Nutrition food significantly reduced duration of menoxenia ($P < 0.01$).

Fig.4 Nutrition food significantly reduced volume of abnormal menstrual bleeding ($P < 0.01$).

Fig.5 Nutrition food significantly reduced volume of abnormal menstrual bleeding (Self-comparison method)(Significantly effective: menstrual bleeding is reduced by over 50%; Effective: menstrual bleeding is reduced by 10-50%; Lack of effective: menstrual bleeding is reduced by less than 10% or increased).

5. Conclusion

The results showed that nutrition foods containing composite components of fruits, vegetables and plants significantly alleviated both primary dysmenorrhea and secondary dysmenorrhea as well as menoxenia.

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